

**The empowerment of the African American Youth through the
portrayal of Miles Morales as Spider-Man**

In what way has the portrayal of Miles Morales in the Spider-Man franchise (2018-2024) influenced the identity empowerment of African American Youth?

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Introduction

Spider-Man debuted in *Amazing Fantasy #15* in 1962. Stan Lee introduced him as a teenage superhero, and his success led to the launch of *The Amazing Spider-Man* in 1963. For decades, the franchise focused on white protagonists, limiting racial representation. As a result, Black youth struggled to identify with mainstream superheroes. Years later, Miles Morales debuted in *Ultimate Comics: Fallout #4* in 2011. Brian Michael Bendis and Sara Pichelli created him as an Afro-Latino Spider-Man. His character redefined the role and addressed identity and discrimination (Marie Mills, 2022, p. 1). Furthermore, Sociopolitical changes in the U.S. influenced his creation. Barack Obama's election and Donald Glover's influence reignited debates on diversity in superhero stories. These events inspired Morales's development. His success reflects the demand for diversity in superheroes and media in "Obama's America" (Marie Mills, 2022, p. 1). Many young people struggle to relate to heroes who don't look like them. For years, mainstream media reinforced this exclusivity. Miles Morales challenges that pattern. His story redefines Spider-Man and offers African American youth a relatable role model.

For this reason, it is relevant to ask: **How has the portrayal of Miles Morales in the Spider-Man franchise (2018-2023) influenced the identity empowerment of African American youth?** The guiding hypothesis suggests that Morales's portrayal significantly empowers African American youth by providing a strong, relatable role model who challenges traditional racial stereotypes in mainstream media. This study is particularly relevant as it explores the potential for Miles Morales to influence identity formation and inspire change among young audiences, especially within a media landscape still struggling with representation issues. The

analysis focuses on *Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse* (2018) and *Spider-Man: Across the Spider-Verse* (2023).

This study uses qualitative analysis. It examines books, academic sources, media reviews, and scholarly articles. Public reactions from social media, blogs, and testimonies contribute to the discussion. Key film scenes highlight Morales's identity and influence. It also explores his connection to social movements like Black Lives Matter and his impact on media diversity.

This research consists of two main sections. The first examines what makes Morales a unique Spider-Man and how he expands African American representation. It analyzes the cultural elements that shape his identity and reinforce his connection to the black community. The second section discusses blackness as a form of power and examines public reactions, testimonies, and media discussions to understand how his representation influences identity, self-perception, and activism.

CHAPTER I: The Portrayal of Miles Morales

1. 1 Miles Morales

Figure 1.

Miles Morales

Note. From *Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse* [Film Still], by Sony Pictures Animation, 2018. Copyright 2018 by Sony Pictures. Retrieved from *personal screenshot* at -1:34:41.

In both films, Miles Morales (figure 1) faces challenges that test his identity and role as Spider-Man. At the beginning of *Into the Spider-Verse*, Miles starts studying at a boarding school after passing a difficult entrance exam, proving his intelligence. His family belongs to the middle class, with his father working as a police officer and his mother as a nurse. He feels closer to his uncle Aaron, who has a more rebellious lifestyle. After a radioactive spider bites Miles, he gains powers but doesn't know how to use them. However, his life changes when he witnesses Kingpin, a powerful crime boss, kill Peter Parker, the original spider-man. Kingpin is using a dangerous machine to open portals to other universes. The machine brings different versions of spider-man into Miles's world, including Gwen Stacy and Peter B. Parker. They try to teach Miles to be a hero, but he lacks confidence. Things get worse when he learns that his uncle is the Prowler, one of Kingpin's enforcers. When Aaron realizes Miles is spider-man, he refuses to hurt him. Consequently, Kingpin kills Aaron for hesitating. This loss pushes Miles to believe in himself. Eventually, he defeats Kingpin, stops the machine, and saves the city (Persichetti, Ramsey, &

Rothman, 2018). *Across the Spider-verse* presents a more confident Miles who feels lonely because he doesn't know other spider-people. He meets Gwen again and discovers the spider society, a group that protects the multiverse. Miguel O'Hara, the leader, tells Miles that all spiderpeople must experience a tragic event to stabilize their universes. Specifically, he warns Miles that his father is supposed to die. Morales refuses to accept his fate and tries to escape. Unexpectedly, he accidentally travels to the wrong universe, where the spider that bit him never existed. In this alternate world, another version of Miles is the Prowler. Trapped, Miles must find a way to escape and save his father before it's too late (Dos Santos, Powers, & Thompson, 2023). These films show Morales's journey from a confused teenager to a hero who refuses to follow a tragic destiny. Miles' story highlights the struggle between fate and choice, making him a unique and inspiring spider-man. Finally, Miles proves he can create his future and be the hero his world needs.

1.2. Miles Morales as a Unique Spider-Man

Peter Parker's prevalence as spider-man in mainstream media has shown a limited narrative of heroism that excludes racial minorities. Peter Parker represents teenage struggles from the 1960s. His narrative promotes a white and heteronormative model of heroism. This model excludes other perspectives and centers the experience of the white middle class. A critical evaluation of this phenomenon shows that Parker's supposed universality homogenizes heroism and marginalizes other identities and experiences. While Peter Parker remains iconic, his narrative doesn't reflect all youth experiences. Miles Morales emerges from this gap and offers a new perspective that challenges the traditional model of heroism.

Miles Morales introduces a new spider-man who reflects intersectional realities and challenges the traditional superhero image. Unlike Peter Parker, who represents white middle-class values, Miles embraces racial, cultural, and class identities. Powell (2020) argues that Miles adds depth because he balances personal responsibility, community ties, and systemic challenges (p. 89), offering a more inclusive and realistic vision of heroism. Analyzing Miles Morales' story, we see that he faces systemic challenges and provides a more inclusive and realistic vision of heroism. Miles reflects W. E. B. Du Bois's (1903) concept of double consciousness. This describes the conflict between two opposing identities. In his case, it appears in his need to adapt to environments with different expectations, his home community and his elite school. Evaluating this aspect, we observe that this duality is not just a narrative trait but a critical reflection of the struggles racialized youth face. Similarly, Hall's representation theory substantiates this analysis. Miles disrupts conventional superhero paradigms through the reconceptualization of heroism and racial identity. Hall demonstrates that representation constitutes rather than reflects reality; consequently, Miles fabricates intersectional realities within media discourse rather than merely portrays them. Analyzing this within the superhero film framework, we see that Miles' story brings diversity and questions the universality of the hero figure. In short, the inclusion of superheroes in cinema generates questions about the limits of representation. For example, does their character genuinely subvert the traditionally white heroic paradigm, or merely repurpose it for inclusive appeal?

1.3. Significance of African Americans' Representation

The superhero genre has perpetuated white dominance, and that leaves black youth without relatable heroes. Miles Morales' change this with his portrayal in spider-verse validates black experiences and reshapes perceptions. When the black community see a black superhero, it has the power to change self-images. For years, the lack of black superheroes or their limited roles suggested that heroism and greatness were traits primarily associated with white characters. This can lead young African Americans to believe power and significance are not part of their identity. Seeing oneself in positions of power positively impacts identity formation, boosting self-esteem and cultural pride. This is particularly important considering that, as scholars point out, mass media play an essential role in shaping both cultural and individual identity. They argue that media influence how individuals perceive the world and themselves, and contribute to the development of socially critical personal attributes:

“Television and the Internet are indispensable in the process of shaping a person's personality, influencing the standards of behavior and moral principles derived from the social environment..., play an important role in shaping individual identity by presenting compelling subjective images and offering avenues for self-expression” (Adila et al, 2022, p. 3)

In this context, the character of Miles Morales shifts the dynamic by providing a relatable role model. Unlike Black Panther, who embodies royalty, Miles represents the everyday experiences of many black youth in the U.S., Miles illustrates cultural roots and personal struggles. His presence enriches the superhero narrative with emotional and inclusive depth. He demonstrates how representation in popular culture can foster identity formation, resilience, and pride among historically

marginalized communities. Authentic representation is achieved through the character of Miles. A new vision of what black characters can be is offered. His presence marks a breakthrough in black superhero representation. The film increases african american visibility without focusing exclusively on racial trauma. As Dru Jeffries (2023) notes, Miles serves as an "ambassador of 21st-century america's diversity," (pag. 4) and preserves cultural authenticity while reaching a wide audience. However, can one character represent such a broad experience? He cannot represent every reality, but his portrayal opens space for richer and more varied narratives.

1.4. Cultural and Visual Identity in the Films

Miles Morales' visual design reinforces his african american identity through his clothing. He wears air jordan 1 "chicago" as a style choice and a black cultural connection. Sneakers symbolize self-expression and success in black communities, unlike previous spider-men, whose costumes lacked cultural specificity, Miles' footwear grounds him in authentic tradition. His shoes create a meaningful representation that resonates with black youth. The air jordan 1 has long been associated with black excellence, largely because Michael Jordan became a cultural icon. These sneakers are widely recognized in hip-hop and urban communities. They reflect a legacy of achievement and resilience (Nike, 2018). By featuring them as a central element of Miles' design, the film visually links him to this history. It reinforces that black identity can be celebrated through fashion. Moreover, his decision to wear the jordans even after customizing his spider-man suit shows something important. Sneakers have been defined as markers through which social and economic identities are expressed (Hooks, 2002, p. 8). This is evident in the film *Into the*

spider-verse. The superhero persona of Miles does not erase his cultural roots; it affirms them. His air jordans reflect a paradox. They represent cultural pride but also commercialization. Society both admires and criminalizes them. Black youth stand at the center of this contradiction. However, the film avoids direct critique. It chooses empowerment instead. Some may believe they are just shoes, but in this context they carry cultural meaning. Can a commercial object still hold genuine cultural power? Does celebrating identity through consumer goods risk reinforcing the very systems that commodify it?

The identity of Miles as an african american is affirmed through the color palette of the movie *spider-verse*. The black suit worn by Miles is interpreted as a sign of empowerment. The use of red and black tones symbolizes passion and mortality. This combination resolves into faith which is the essential spirit of *spider-man*. The blue in Peter Parker's suit symbolizes traditional heroism and conformity. It represents the white superhero model. In contrast, Miles' black suit often seen as transgressive in the west becomes redefined in african american culture. In that context it is a symbol of resistance. This visual shift is significant. superhero films have typically marginalized black characters. they often link them to aggression. In *black panther* (2018), black became a symbol of royalty and power. It countered the historical use of the color to marginalize racialized communities. Movements like black lives matter have reinforced this shift. They have turned black into an emblem of resistance against oppression. Longshore (1979) notes that black has been used to reinforce negative stereotypes. It has associated african americans with criminality or transgression, by making this color his emblem, Miles breaks from

spider-man's visual canon. He joins a tradition of black heroes who challenge white hegemony in how power is represented. Some might argue that the black in his suit is just a stylistic choice. They might say it has no political meaning. However that view ignores the deep cultural history behind the color. Miles' design carries intentionality. It says that identity matters and says that color, clothing, and symbol all tell a story. Although in a medium where black has been used to symbolize the threatening, Miles transforms it into a sign of strength and resistance, reaffirming his identity.

The spider-verse films distinguish themselves through innovative music usage. Miles Morales' soundtrack works as an extension of his identity. The film's music plays a crucial role in shaping Miles' character. In both films hip-hop serves as an essential part of his identity and not just background sound. Hip-hop plays an important role as an expressive medium for the black community. The filmmakers integrate cultural elements into the narrative thoughtfully. Baker-Mason (2020) says that Miles' musical identity is a core aspect of the story. This integration adds depth to his character. It allows him to break typical superhero tropes. He becomes a multidimensional figure. The soundtrack enhances the audience's understanding of Miles. It also improves representation in superhero films and avoids stereotypes and supports his development across the film. Some critics argue that linking Miles to hip-hop reinforces stereotypes about black identity. However the film uses this link as a form of agency. It lets Miles show his identity beyond simple or reductive portrayals (Baker-Mason, 2020). His musical taste fits naturally into who he is. It shows that people in these communities are more than what media often shows. In essence, the

soundtrack empowers Miles and it also strengthens his connection with the black community.

Miles Morales represents a significant advancement in African American superhero representation through three key elements. His visual design features cultural markers that resonate with African American audiences, turning the black in his suit into a symbol of power. The film's soundtrack incorporates hip-hop as a genuine part of his identity, moving beyond stereotypes. These aspects create a meaningful representation. Miles isn't just a black spider-man; his cultural identity shapes his heroism and enriches the superhero genre.

CHAPTER II: Empowerment of African American Youth

2.1 Blackness as Power

Miles Morales empowers African American youth by making Blackness a source of strength, not a barrier. His identity is central to his heroism, not something to overcome. Vidal (2023) claims, "his heritage is integral to the movie, a source of strength, and part of what makes him an incredible spider-man. The result is an empowering watch for anyone" (parr. 5) challenging the notion that heroes should separate from their roots. Miles's Black identity is integral to the story, as it serves as a source of power rather than a mere accessory. The film avoids tokenism and does not justify Miles through educational narratives. Miles redefines Black representation by showcasing Blackness as a source of power and affirming self-sufficiency, while steering clear of stereotypes. However, the film primarily explores his dual identity as spider-man, which, while avoiding trauma-based narratives, leaves some systemic racial issues unaddressed. Some critics identify certain limitations, but these do not diminish Miles' fundamental achievement. Black identity may be commodified for mainstream consumption. However, representation visibility is paradoxically increased through this commercialization. Miles remains secondary to Peter Parker's legacy. Yet heroism is redefined through this positioning. African American youth are decisively empowered by Miles. Blackness is transformed into a source of strength rather than a barrier. His heroism directly stems from his cultural identity. This demonstrates that authentic power is generated through embracing rather than rejecting one's heritage. Even so, Miles transforms the narrative paradigm and shows that Blackness constitutes empowerment rather than encumbrance.

2.2. Testimonies of Identification and Validation

Miles Morales as an african american spider-man is crucial, as it allows black youth to identify with a protagonist in heroic stories where they were previously underrepresented. The phrase "Anyone can wear the mask" from Miles' movies symbolizes universal inclusion. Gonzales (2023) Notes that it suggests superhero identities are not exclusive to white characters and promotes an empowering message of accessibility. However, this phrase reveals a vital contradiction: if anyone can truly be a superhero, why have there been so few prominent Black superheroes in mainstream media? This tension demonstrates that simply declaring inclusion is not enough; it must be visually represented to challenge the implicit racial structures within superhero stories. Miles Morales' representation is significant because when "Anyone can wear the mask" is embodied by an african american character, it transforms from an abstract idea into a powerful reality. Taking into account the words of Shameik Moore, the african american actor who voices Morales. He states: "I really learned about humanity and it furthered the connection between every, all of us." (Moore, 2024, 41:24) Here, he positions himself as a learner affected by the role; the story resonates and transforms the performer. The phrase furthered the connection suggests that representation deepens empathy across different racial and cultural groups. He then says: "I had to see different ethnicities and cultures come out and cry when they see me because of my voice." (Moore, 2024, 40:55) This moment reveals the emotional power of recognition; his voice alone triggered tears, which proves that even auditory presence has representational weight. The verb cry signals deep identification, not just admiration. Moore then adds: "Miles is the version of me... that went to that dance battle for the first time... I was scared, I'mma jump off

this building though.” (Moore, 2024, 38:03) This personal comparison shows that Miles embodies his own fear and bravery; the metaphor of the jump off the building recalls the central scene of the film and symbolizes the emotional leap that marks the moment of becoming visible. Finally, Moore admits: “I knew it’d be good... but I had to witness it to believe it.” His word witness shows the film’s unexpected emotional depth, even for its creators. Taking into account other testimonies, Betancourt (2018) highlights the line: “Miles is all those things I am, plus a superhero. And not just any superhero. The superhero. Spider-Man.” (parr. 3) This quote expresses the subject’s sense of identification with Miles; “all those things I am” affirms shared identity. The phrase “plus a superhero” signals aspirational transformation. The repetition “superhero” marks Miles’s rise to canonical status. The speaker is central. Another statement “Finally, the real me in a movie — where the real me is Spider-Man. It was thrilling.” (Bentacourt, 2018, parr. 23) stresses delayed recognition. “Finally” reveals past exclusion; “the real me” repeated, affirms authentic representation. “In a movie” points to mass media as a space of visibility. In a nutshell, for many, Miles is the first spider-man who reflects their identity.

2.3. A Symbol of Empowerment

Artists and activists use Miles Morales to represent and empower young african americans in movements like black lives matter. Miles Morales embodies the struggle for identity and self-determination. His story as a young afro-latino hero makes him a role model for those seeking representation and strength in spaces of protest and social change.

Figure 2.

A Hero in Protest

*Note. From *Before Father's Day is Over, I Had a Thought About Miles and His Dad* [Instagram post], by @marcusthevisual, 2020. Copyright 2020 by @marcusthevisual. Retrieved from https://www.instagram.com/p/CBuQ_uFICdy/?igsh=MXFkbGVwYnc0NGxwdQ%3D%3D*

Artist Marcus The Visual portrays Miles Morales at a black lives matter protest (figure 2), wearing a shirt with the movement's slogan and a "*No Justice, No Peace*" belt. Amid the protest, Miles's father, a police officer, confronts him while his mother attempts to mediate. This scene emphasizes Miles as a symbol of resistance and unity, showcasing his determination as a young African American. His father represents authority, while his mother embodies community balance. Turns Miles into a model of courage and conviction. Marcus The Visual chooses Miles Morales because his story speaks of identity and personal power. His presence at the protest emphasizes the importance of African American youth in social movements. More than a fictional hero, Miles is a symbol that inspires others to stand up for their beliefs and claim spaces for transformation. Miles Morales represents empowerment and highlights the importance of representation in fiction for the African American struggle, strengthening identity and leadership in real life.

If Marcus The Visual presents Miles Morales as a symbol of resistance, real-life protesters redefine him as an active force in movements like black lives matter. Protesters wear Miles Morales's suit because his story reflects their struggles. His dual identity as both hero and marginalized youth mirrors the challenges young black individuals face. By embodying him, they transform his fictional fight into real activism.

Figure 3.

Morales in the Streets

Note. From *Black Lives Matter Protest Featuring Miles Morales* [Photograph], by @JSCOSPLAYART, 2020. Copyright 2020 by @JSCOSPLAYART. Retrieved from <https://www.newsweek.com/spiderman-protest-black-new-york-1509343>.

Naiquan, a Black protester in New York, marched in Black Lives Matter protests (Figure 3) both as himself and as spider-man in Miles's suit. He climbed the Manhattan Bridge, turning the character into a direct statement against injustice. His presence resonated deeply. Children saw a superhero fighting for them. Adults recognized Miles as a symbol of defiance and empowerment. Naiquan did not

choose Peter Parker, he chose Miles Morales because Miles represents Black youth demanding justice. Naiquan wore Miles's suit because this character embodies resistance, identity, and leadership. Miles is not just a superhero, he is a call to action. His image mobilizes people, proving that representation does not just inspire, it empowers. Marcus The Visual reimagines Miles as a protester, and activists like Naiquan turn his story into real-world resistance, making him a symbol of change.

Conclusion

To answering the research question, the portrayal of Miles Morales in the spider-man franchise (2018–2023) has played a significant role in empowering african american youth. We can assert that his character serves as a strong and relatable role model; he challenges racial stereotypes. Miles creates new avenues for representation within mainstream media. Throughout both films, Miles Morales transcends the traditional role of the superhero; and he emerges as a cultural symbol of empowerment, particularly for black communities. His narrative resonates with contemporary social movements such as black lives matter, which advocate for justice and increased visibility for historically marginalized groups like africans americans. Miles reflects the daily struggles faced by many young individuals. As have been mentioned in this analysis elements for example air jordans, her suit and the presence of hip-hop rhythms function as meaningful expressions of resistance and cultural pride; they connect his character directly to the lived experiences of his audience. However the influence of Miles Morales extends beyond cinematic representation. He reminds them that their voices carry weight; he demonstrates that they, too, can become agents of change within their communities and broader society. Nonetheless his legacy provokes important questions. Will Miles open the door for a broader range of diverse heroes, or will he remain an isolated figure in an industry still shaped by dominant racial paradigms? Can other franchises achieve the same level of authentic integration of diversity as spider-verse with Miles Morales? Besides, while this essay has focused on elements in both films and public reaction, a further area of exploration could involve examining how rhetorical devices also contribute to the film's construction of identity empowerment. Additionally, future

research might investigate in what way Miles Morales compares with other superhero films in representing marginalized voices.

References

- Adila, A., Imam, I., Sultan, D., Nurlaila, N., Vitriani, I., Purwanto, E., Rahma, A., & Kristian, A. (2022). The Role of Mass Media in Shaping People's Cultural Identity. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 35(2), 559-565. Retrieved November 6, 2024 from doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.52155/ijpsat.v45.1.6226>
- Baker-Mason, J. (8 January 2020). The Spider-Man: Into the Spideverse Album is Redefining What it Means to be African-American and Latinx. *Medium*. Retrieved March 29, 2025 from <https://medium.com/@bakemas/the-spider-man-into-the-spideverse-album-is-redefining-what-it-means-to-be-african-american-and-58c1f755a3af>
- Betancourt, D. (2018, December 13). Miles Morales is a Spider-Man who's biracial like me. So why wasn't I more excited for his movie? *The Washington Post*. Retrieved July 29, 2025, from <https://www.washingtonpost.com/arts-entertainment/2018/12/13/miles-morales-is-spider-man-whos-biracial-like-me-so-why-wasnt-i-more-excited-his-movie/>
- Dos Santos, J. P., Powers, K., & Thompson, J. (Directors). (2023). *Spider-Man: Across the Spider-Verse* [Film]. Sony Pictures Animation.
- Dru Jeffries, "‘Anyone Can Wear the Mask’: The Marginalization of Miles Morales in Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse," *JCMS* 62, no. 5 (2022–2023): 192–214
- Du Bois, W. E. B. (1903, February 1). The souls of Black folk. Atlanta, Ga.: A. C. McClurg & Co. Retrieved May 21, 2025, from <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/408/408-h/408-h.htm>
- Gonzalez, A. (2023). *Into the Spider-Verse: Cultural Identity in Spider-Man Media*. *Into the Spider-Verse: Cultural Identity in Spider-Man Media*. Whittier College. Retrieved November 6, 2024 from <https://poetcommons.whittier.edu/scholars/33>
- Hooks, C. S. (2022). *What's my superpower?: The interconnection that exist through sneakers and the commodification of Blackness* [Tesis de maestría inédita]. Fordham University. <https://research.library.fordham.edu/dissertations/AAI29207442>
- Longshore, D. (1979). Color Connotations and Racial Attitudes. *Journal of Black Studies*, 9(4), 183-197. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002193477900900403>
- Marie Mills, R. (2022). A Post-Soul Spider-Man: The Remixed Heroics of Miles Morales. *The Black Scholar*, 52(1), 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00064246.2022.2007345>
- Michael, C. (2020). *Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse: Youth, Race, and the Hypertext*. New York. Routledge.

- Moore, S.. (10 de septiembre de 2024). *Shameik Moore manifested his role as Miles Morales in Spiderman | Bars and Nuggets* [Video]. Amazon Music. Retrieved July 29, 2025, from <https://youtu.be/8l6TYBnPnCo?si=YJYsbICEnTSYcV9q>
- Naiquan. (2020, June 12). [Picture]. Newsweek. Retrieved November 6, 2025, from <https://www.newsweek.com/spiderman-protest-black-new-york-1509343>
- Nike, Inc. (2018). Air Jordan I Origin Story. Nike. Retrieved November 6, 2025, from <https://www.nike.com/es/launch/t/air-jordan-1-origin-story>
- Persichetti, B., Ramsey, P., & Rothman, R. (Directors). (2018). Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse [Film]. United States: Sony Pictures Animation.
- Powell, Brian. (2020). Representation and Metaphors for Civil Rights in Marvel Comics, *Vulcan Historical Review: Vol. 24, Article 20*. Retrieved November 6, 2024, from <https://digitalcommons.library.uab.edu/vulcan/vol24/iss2020/20>
- Visual, M. [@marcusthevisual]. (2024, November 7). Before Father's Day is over, I had a thought about Miles and his dad [Instagram photograph] [Post]. Instagram. Retrieved November 7, 2024, from https://www.instagram.com/p/CBuQ_uFICdy/?igsh=MXFkbGVwYnc0NGxwdQ%3D%3D
- Vidal, A. (13 June 2023). Across the Spider-Verse Hits Harder for Black, Brown, & Latine Viewers. *Medium*. Retrieved March 29, 2025, from <https://medium.com/@angelowrites/across-the-spider-verse-hits-harder-for-black-brown-latine-viewers-a4aeb9531437>